

A Study of Complex Compounds of N-Benzenesulphonyl Glycines with Some Metal Ions. Part XII. N-*p* Toluenesulphonyl Glycine

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N-*p* Toluenesulphonyl glycine (R_tH_2) forms complex compounds with Cu(II), Ag(I), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II). With Cu(II), the compounds isolated are $Cu(R_tH)(OH)(H_2O)H_2O$, $Cu(R_tH)_2$, $[Cu(R_tH)(OH)]_2$ and $Na_2Cu(R_t)_2$. Zn(II) and Cd(II) forms *bis*-complexes, but Cd(II) is also found to give $Cd(R_tH)(OH)(H_2O)$. With Ag(I) one complex $Ag(R_tH)$ is obtained in the pure state. Hg(II) compounds have composition $Hg(R_tH)(OH)(H_2O)$ and $K_2Hg(R_t)_2$. Magnetic data of all Cu(II) complexes and electronic and i.r. spectral data of most Cu(II) complexes as well as some of N-benzenesulphonyl glycine (R_bH_2) are recorded. By potentiometric titration pK_2^* and pK_1^* of weak dibasic acids $Cu(R_tH)_2$ and $Cu(R_bH)_2$ have been evaluated and a discussion has been made.

In continuation of our work¹ with N-benzenesulphonyl (dl) α - and β - alanines ($R_b^\alpha H_2$ and $R_b^\beta H_2$), N-*p*- toluenesulphonyl glycine (R_tH_2) has been found to form compounds with Cu(II), Ag(I), Hg(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II). Complexes isolated are closely comparable to those of N-benzenesulphonyl glycine (R_bH_2)² and ($R_b^\alpha H_2$)¹. Cu(II) complexes isolated are $Cu(R_tH)(OH)(H_2O)H_2O$, $[Cu(R_tH)(OH)]_2$, $Cu(R_tH)_2$, and $Na_2Cu(R_t)_2$. Kachhwaha and Gaur³ from potentiometric study obtained an indication of a 2 : 1 complex of R_tH_2 with Cu(II).

With Zn(II) and Cd(II), *bis*-complexes $Zn(R_tH)_2$ and $Cd(R_tH)_2$ are obtained. Cd(II) is also found to give $Cd(R_tH)(OH)(H_2O)$. Ag(I) forms the compound $Ag(R_tH)$ and two compounds $Hg(R_tH)(OH)(H_2O)$ and $K_2Hg(R_t)_2H_2O$ are obtained with Hg(II).

The compounds $Cu(R_bH)_2$ and $Cu(R_tH)_2$ are weak dibasic acids. By potentiometric titration at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) their pK_2^* and pK_1^* are evaluated by projection-strip method⁴ as well as by Bjerrum's *half- \bar{n}* -method with subsequent correction⁵. Magnetic moment values of all Cu(II) complexes of R_tH_2 and some of R_bH_2 and electronic spectra of aqueous solution of $Cu(R_tH)_2$, $Na_2Cu(R_t)_2$, $Cu(R_bH)_2$ and $Na_2Cu(R_b)_2$ have been measured at room temperature and i.r. spectra of $Cu(R_tH)_2$, $[Cu(R_tH)(OH)]_2$, $Na_2Cu(R_t)_2$, R_bH_2 and KR_tH have also been recorded in KBr matrix.

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EXPERIMENTAL

N-p Toluenesulphonyl glycine was prepared following the method stated in the literature⁶, m.p. 149–150°. Found: Eqv. wt. 227.3; Calc. 229. It is soluble in warm alcohol, hot water and sparingly so in cold water.

Methods of isolation of complex compounds of Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Ag(I) and Hg(II) with R_tH_2 are almost similar to the isolation of such complexes¹ with $R_b^aH_2$. Complex compounds isolated and their analyses are stated in Table I.

TABLE I
Analyses of metal complexes

Compound	% Metal		% Nitrogen		% Sodium or Potassium		% Loss at 110°	
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Cu(R_tH)(OH)(H ₂ O), H ₂ O	18.67	18.44	4.29	4.06			10.50	10.45
[Cu(R_tH)(OH)] ₂	20.66	20.58	4.67	4.54				
Cu(R_tH) ₂	12.00	12.23	5.33	5.39				
Na ₂ Cu(R_t) ₂	11.47	11.27	4.94	4.97	8.00	8.16		
Hg(R_tH)(OH)(H ₂ O)	43.34	43.20	2.98	3.02				
K ₂ Hg(R_t) ₂ , H ₂ O	26.22	26.71	3.59	3.73	10.20	10.41	2.44	2.40
K ₂ Hg(R_t) ₂	27.10	27.37	3.89	3.82				
Ag(R_tH)	32.50	32.15	4.38	4.17				
Zn(R_tH) ₂	12.30	12.53	5.32	5.38				
Cd(R_tH)(OH)(H ₂ O)	29.49	29.94	3.81	3.73				
Cd(R_tH) ₂	20.15	19.78	4.94	4.93				

By potentiometric titration of Cu(R_bH)₂ and Cu(R_tH)₂ at a temperature $32 \pm 1^\circ$ at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) using requisite amount of NaClO₄ the average number (\bar{n}) of ionisable hydrogen attached to the molecule was calculated and \bar{n} values were plotted against the corresponding pH values. From the curves pK^*_2 and pK^*_1 were evaluated by projection-strip method as well as by Bjerrum's *half- \bar{n}* -method with subsequent correction using equations (1) and (2)

$$K^*_2 = [H^+]^{\bar{n}-1.5} \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{[H^+]^{\bar{n}-1.5}}{3K^*_1}} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

$$K^*_1 = [H^+]^{\bar{n}-0.5} \times \left(1 + \frac{3[H^+]^{\bar{n}-0.5}}{K^*_2} \right) \quad \dots (2)$$

Values of pK^*_2 and pK^*_1 for Cu(R_bH)₂ and Cu(R_tH)₂ are stated in Table II. Values of pK^*_2 and pK^*_1 for Cu(R_b^aH)₂ are also included for comparison. The results reported here are based on duplicate titrations made under identical conditions.

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TABLE II

Acid dissociation constants of Cu(II) complexes—Cu(RH)₂

Compounds	Values obtained by Projection-strip method		Values obtained by Bjerrum's <i>half-n</i> -method with subsequent correction	
	pK ₂ *	pK ₁ *	pK ₂ *	pK ₁ *
Cu(R _b H) ₂	4.51	7.23	4.51	7.23
Cu(R _t H) ₂	4.55	7.24	4.55	7.26
Cu(R _b ^a H) ₂	4.70	7.10	4.71	7.09

The magnetic moment values after correction for diamagnetism of all Cu(II) complexes and electronic spectra of water soluble Cu(II) chelates, ligands R_tH₂ and R_bH₂ and their sodium salts NaR_tH and NaR_bH were measured at (room temperature 30±1°) and their data are stated in Table III. The i.r. spectra of Cu(R_tH)₂, [Cu(R_tH)(OH)]₂, Na₂Cu(R_t)₂, R_tH₂ and KR_tH have been studied and the assignments^{7,12} of some important vibrations are recorded in Table IV.

DISCUSSION

For most Cu(II) compounds⁸ having square planar or distorted octahedral structure the observed magnetic moment values are 1.8–2.2 B.M. Of course there are many Cu(II) compounds having subnormal values⁹. In the present cases normal values are obtained excepting those of weak acids—Cu(R_bH)₂ and Cu(R_tH)₂ where subnormal values have been found. This has also been observed in the Cu(II) chelates¹ of the ligand R_b^aH₂. This low value may be due to metal-metal interaction in an octahedral structure where the remaining coordination position is occupied by a carbonyl oxygen of a second molecular unit. The normal magnetic moment values of the sodium salts may be due to interposition of large Na⁺ ion between adjacent molecular units, breaking the dimeric structure of the acids. But the same value (1.85 B.M.) has also been observed in the case of lithium salt, Li₂Cu(R_b^a)₂ having much smaller cation. However, the dimeric nature of the compounds Cu(R_bH)₂ and Cu(R_tH)₂ is also supported by i.r. spectral data.

It has been observed that the separation between antisymmetrical and symmetrical COO⁻ stretching vibrations and the direction to which they are individually shifted on bond formation as compared with free carboxylate anion depend upon metal oxygen bonding type^{10,11}. Data in Table IV show that in the cases of [Cu(R_tH)(OH)]₂ and Na₂Cu(R_t)₂, the antisymmetrical bands have been shifted to higher frequencies whereas the symmetrical

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TABLE III

Magnetic data of Cu(II) complexes and electronic spectral data of water soluble Cu(II) complexes and ligands

Compound	μ_{eff} in B.M.	Temperature in °K	λ_{max}^{aa} in m μ	log ϵ
Cu(R _t H)(OH)(H ₂ O), H ₂ O	2.01	303		
[Cu(R _t H)(OH)] ₂	1.92	303		
Cu(R _t H) ₂	1.37	303	760	1.31
			320	1.86
			273	2.95
			262	3.20
			232	4.14
Na ₂ Cu(R _t) ₂	1.85	302	660	1.66
			310sh	2.55
			272sh	3.23
			263sh	3.48
			223	4.16
Cu(R _v H) ₂	1.38	303	760	1.26
			320	1.73
			271	2.89
			263	2.95
			258	3.01
			231	3.80
Na ₂ Cu(R _v) ₂	1.83	303	660	1.66
			310sh	2.81
			272	3.39
			263	3.44
			225	4.10
R _t H ₂			300sh	1.30
			271	2.61
			264	2.78
			234	3.96
NaR _t H			271	2.54
			262	2.80
			225	4.00
R _v H ₂			295sh	1.32
			271	2.87
			263	2.93
			259	2.80
			234	3.45
NaR _v H			271	2.80
			264	2.89
			224	3.84

TABLE IV

I.R. spectral data of Cu(II) complexes and ligands

R_1H_2	Frequencies cm^{-1}				Assignments (probable)
	KR_1H	$Cu(R_1H)_2$	$[Cu(R_1H)(OH)]_2$	$Na_2Cu(R_1)_2$	
3350(b st)	...	3500(b m)			N-H stretching
...	3400-				Overlapping of N-H and C-H stretchings.
	2700(b st)				
...			3600-		Broad bands due to overlapping of associated N-H and O-H, and C-H stretchings.
			2900(b st)		
2962(b st)			Carboxylic acid O-H stretching combined with other bands particularly C-H stretchings.
2941(b st)					
2860(b st)					
2630(b st)					
1724(sp st)	due to -COOH.
...	1625(b st)	1645(b st)	1636(sp st)	1644(b st)	COO ⁻ antisymmetrical stretching.
...	1565(sh m)	..	due to lattice or coordinated water.
1444(b m)	C-O stretching or O-H deformation.
...	1394(b st)	1418(b st)	1389(sp m)	1390(b st)	COO ⁻ symmetrical stretching.
1345(sp st)	1343(b st)	1328(b st)	1269(b st)	1265(sp st)	due to SO ₂ N < group.
1240(b st)	C-O stretching or O-H deformation.
1164(sp st)	1170(b st)	1168(b st)	1148(b st)	1146(b st)	due to SO ₂ N < group
...	1100(b m)	...	due to M-OH bending mode (Bridging OH groups).
825(st m)	810(sp st)	818(sp m)	820(sp st)	816(sp st)	C-H out of plane deformation (Benzene ring in favour of <i>p</i> substitution).
725(sp st)	720(sp st)	710(b m)	726(sp st)	715(sp st)	
660(b st)	668(b st)	665(b m)	680(sp st)	666(b st)	
...	...	570(b st)	605(b st)	575(b st)	M-N stretching.
...	...	550(b st)	569(b st)	558(b st)	M-O stretching.

sp = sharp; b = broad; sh = shoulder; st = strong; m = medium; w = weak.

bands have been shifted to lower frequencies as compared with those of free carboxylate anion. This indicates the presence of $-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{O}-\text{M}$ type of bonding supporting square planar structure. But in the case of $Cu(R_1H)_2$ both the stretching vibrations are shifted to the same direction i.e., higher frequencies. This is compatible with the equivalence of bonding of the two carboxyl oxygens.

The band near 1100 cm^{-1} has been assigned by Nakamoto¹² to be due to the M-OH bending mode in compounds containing bridging O-H groups. Similar band has been found in the spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{R}_t\text{H})(\text{OH})]_2$ at 1100 cm^{-1} supporting dimeric nature of the complex with diol bridge arrangements. The band at 1565 cm^{-1} due to co-ordinated or lattice water may be regarded for the existence of the following tautomeric equilibrium :

The i.r. spectral data show a marked shift of the band at 1724 cm^{-1} (ligand) to lower frequencies and a shift in $\text{SO}_2\text{N}<$ stretching frequencies from 1345 cm^{-1} (ligand) to lower frequencies in the complexes. They provide evidences of metal oxygen and metal nitrogen bonding respectively. The bands for M-N and M-O stretching frequencies in the complexes are also observed as shown in Table IV. The disappearance of N-H stretching in $\text{Na}_2\text{Cu}(\text{R}_t)_2$ supports the dissociation of imido-hydrogen and the formation of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}_t)_2^{2-}$ ion.

Electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes show characteristic absorption bands in the region $900\text{--}600\text{ m}\mu$ ¹³. In aqueous solution the absorption maxima at $660\text{ m}\mu$ for $\text{Na}_2\text{Cu}(\text{R}_b)_2$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{Cu}(\text{R}_t)_2$ whereas those of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}_b\text{H})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{R}_t\text{H})_2$ at $760\text{ m}\mu$ are observed. Thus on salt formation the band of the acid at $760\text{ m}\mu$ suffers a shift to shorter wavelength at $660\text{ m}\mu$. However, ϵ_{max} values of both acids and salts support distorted octahedral arrangement in aqueous solution¹⁴, evidently due to water interaction. The monomeric nature of $\text{Cu}(\text{R}_b\text{H})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{R}_t\text{H})_2$ in aqueous solution is also supported by potentiometric titration. Absorption peaks in the u-v region are undoubtedly due to ligand molecules as are indicated by high molar extinction coefficient values.

It has already been stated that $\text{Cu}(\text{R}_b\text{H})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{R}_t\text{H})_2$ in aqueous solution behave as weak dibasic acids—evidently this is due to ionisation of imido-hydrogen. Their pK_2^* and pK_1^* values have been determined. The imido-hydrogen of the ligands become more acidic on formation of metal nitrogen coordination bond. The enhancement of acidity appears to be a function of metal nitrogen bond strength or approximately to the stability of metal chelates⁵. So the stability of Cu(II) chelates may be represented in the ligand order $\text{R}_b\text{H}_2 > \text{R}_t\text{H}_2 > \text{R}_b^a\text{H}_2$ and the results are in accordance with the crowding effect.

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